

METHODS OF TEACHING STUDENTS OF MEDICAL UNIVERSITIES THE DISCIPLINE OF INFORMATION TECHNOLOGY IN MEDICINE THROUGH THE ELECTRONIC PLATFORM MODDLE

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Abstract: *Choosing a complex set of tools, commonly referred to as Learning Management Systems (LMS), to create the perfect blend of traditional classroom sessions and the most appropriate e-learning components has become common practice. Our institutions have chosen the open source LMS Moodle. After many years of using it in everyday teaching practice, we were inspired to analyze the effect of this platform. This article presents the results of surveys conducted to familiarize students and teachers with experiments with Moodle.*

Keywords: *learning management system, privacy, security, experience, LMS Moodle, localization.*

Introduction

This article presents the results of two surveys aimed at mapping the experience of students and teachers with the Moodle form. Mostly on these issues, and therefore on the impact of the use of LMS in daily teaching practice on the academic achievements of students, were carried out as part of a bilateral project between our institutions. Participation in the study was voluntary and anonymous for both students and teachers.

Modern educational standards require the use of various tools in addition to the teaching and learning processes, as well as effective assessment. A learning management system is often the backbone of a robust e-learning platform and follows the standards and best practices recommended by respected educational and corporate stakeholders [1-4].

The use of distance learning technologies in the organization of the educational process, the rapid acquisition of new information in science ensures high efficiency. Virtual learning methods allow you to quickly obtain additional information on this issue. The introduction of distance learning technologies into the educational process and the study of methods for their effective use, as well as

the creation of distance learning courses, are one of the most important scientific and technical problems of our time. Based on the foregoing, the use of Moodle in teaching students of higher educational institutions, for teaching information technology in medicine and information technology in educational processes is one of the key topics in the implementation of distance learning technologies in the educational process. The article describes the capabilities of the system (Learning Management Systems - LMS) or virtual learning environments (Virtual Learning Environments - VLE). Moodle is a tool environment for developing both individual online courses and educational websites [12-16].

An open source LMS was evaluated according to a set of minimum criteria that included an active community, stable development status, good documentation, didactic purpose, and emphasis on content presentation and communication features [11-15].

Methods

The results of our research have aroused the interest of many students and teachers, as our Bukhara State Medical Institute accepts foreign students studying in the MBBS program. This group includes students from India, Pakistan and Saudi Arabia, as well as from New York.

In teaching these students, I used the LMS Moodle platform, which is one of the electronic platforms that faculty in developed countries use in their work when I am teaching. With the help of this platform, I taught information technologies in medicine, in the process of passing training sessions on the discipline program, lectures on the topic, practical exercises, laboratory classes, I posted all presentation materials, test questions, video courses. Creating a course on this electronic platform was very easy and interesting for me, because here the teacher has the opportunity to independently create a course according to his lesson, and the performance of the program is very good, creating an electronic course gave me great opportunities even when switching to traditional teaching, because in Moodle the information was placed in all the annual courses based on the ability to come prepared. When students prepare for a lesson, it would be interesting to work with it, and good results would be achieved, and the students would be delighted with it.

In today's information age, teachers of higher education institutions are provided with a very wide range of opportunities for conducting training sessions using open electronic platforms, such as the Moodle electronic platform.

In addition, students can read the information they need when doing homework or self-study topics, and turn in their assignments to the teacher on the Moodle electronic platform, and the teacher can check their assignment.

This gives the student ample opportunity to come at the end of the semester and prepare for the final control or control exams. because the student can get the basic information he needs from the Moodle electronic platform

Based on our experience, I believe that e-learning courses in the natural sciences, created through e-platforms for student self-study and research, will pave the way for students to work independently, think independently, and conduct research in the future. to teach the younger generation to work independently, to think independently from the first year during our lessons.

Conclusion

Summarizing, we can say that, living in the modern age of computer technology, specialists in all areas, including us, teachers, must keep up with the times, using the latest innovative technologies in the educational process, new modern electronic platforms and changing the methods of transition , of course, our university will be among the 100 best universities in the world. places. To do this, we, teachers, must be in constant search.

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